

How do cyclists experience a context-aware prototype warning system? Assessing perceived safety, perception and riding behaviour changes through a field study

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ABSTRACT

The number of bicycle crashes is increasing in many European countries. In the Netherlands, a country well-known for its high-quality cycling infrastructure and cycling culture, bicycle crashes are also increasing, especially for e-bike users. Smart bicycle technologies, such as safety warning support systems, could contribute to reducing crash risk for cyclists. However, perceived safety and trust in these technologies are determinant factors in accepting and using such technologies. This study investigated users' perceived safety, perceived trust, and perceived performance with a context-aware prototype warning system to support cyclists in the real world. In addition, it investigated users' riding behaviour changes when receiving warnings in high crash risk locations by collecting GPS data. The above were evaluated through a field trial experiment using three rides per participant, with the first one serving as a control ride and a follow-up questionnaire after each ride conducted in Enschede, the Netherlands, between April and May 2024, with a sample of 46 participants. Results show that participants' perceived safety increased after they tried out the prototype warning system. In addition, it was found that warning systems positively influence participants' riding behaviour, since they reduced their speed. This study proves the potential benefits of smart bicycle technologies in improving cyclists' safety.

1. Introduction

The number of bicycle crashes and fatalities increases yearly worldwide (European Commission, 2023a; ITF, International Transport Forum, 2023). In Europe, every year, around 2000 cycling fatalities happen, with no decrease since 2011, representing 10 % of all road fatalities (European Commission, 2023a, 2023b). This is probably due to the increased number of people cycling in the last few years and exposure to motor vehicles in many countries with and without cycling culture (European Commission, 2023b; Uijtdewilligen et al., 2022). Moreover, when we account for road fatalities in urban areas, cyclists and other vulnerable road users, such as pedestrians, represent almost 70 % of the total fatalities (European Commission, 2023b). The majority of road fatalities within urban areas involve motor vehicles with cyclists and pedestrians.

The recent report from the International Traffic Safety Data and Analysis Group (IRTAD) shows a discouraging trend in cycling fatalities, especially for e-bike users. The share of e-bike users in cyclist fatalities

has been increasing in many countries, such as Switzerland (55 %), Germany (44 %), Belgium (38 %), and the Netherlands (34 %) (ITF, International Transport Forum, 2023). In the Netherlands, well known for its cycling policies, culture, and infrastructure, cycling fatalities represented 40 % of all road fatalities in 2022, and the e-bike users rate of all cycling fatalities increased by 9 % in 2022 since 2018. This is mainly due to the e-bike users' exposure, age and health factors (Westerhuis et al., 2024). In addition, since 2020, the number of bicycle fatalities in the Netherlands has been higher than that of passenger cars (Statistics Netherlands (CBS), 2023). Therefore, additional actions should be taken to decrease cycling crash risk and bring these numbers down.

1.1. Background

Smart bicycle technologies have rapidly developed over the last decades, aiming to influence cyclists' safety and the general view of bicycles, e-bikes and the future of soft transport modes, especially in the

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era of Internet of Things (IoT) and smart cities (Behrendt, 2016; Oliveira et al., 2021). These technologies and systems have various functionalities that potentially impact road safety (Engbers, 2019; Westerhuis et al., 2021). Smart bicycle technologies may attract more people to cycling since they could offer a sense of increased perceived safety, as well as an actual increase in cyclists' safety. Smart bicycle technologies can assist cyclists in reducing the risk of crashes, collisions with other vehicles, and single-bicycle crashes due to the wide range of applications. However, users' perception of smart bicycle technologies and trust will influence their deployment and penetration rate into the market.

Recently, considerable literature has grown on warning systems aiming to prevent collisions (Kapousizis et al., 2022). Linder et al. (2024) examined users' perceived safety and the effectiveness of a bicycle warning system in reducing crashes and human interaction with autonomous vehicles in different scenarios and intersections using a bicycle simulator. Engbers (2019) examined how technologies, such as front- and rear-view assistance on bicycles, can support older adults by conducting experiments on bicycle simulators and on the road. The findings of this study showed that older adults valued these systems positively, especially the rear-view assistant. In addition, Westerhuis et al. (2021) tested a light communication system to support older adults while cycling. The aim was for the system to display braking and turning intentions, hence, users were aware of the direction of the bicycle and able to press a button to indicate their direction rather than using their arms, which influences cyclists' balance, especially for older adults. Participants of the experiment, both users of the instrumented bicycle and users riding other non-instrumented bicycles who interacted with the system, found the system useful. Another study that investigated users' perspectives of a warning for critical events using a bicycle simulator was conducted by Kreißig et al. (2022). They developed hypothetical critical safety events and warned the participants in a virtual environment. The assessment of this study revealed good ratings regarding trust and acceptance of the warning system and higher acceptance for the young participants (Kreißig et al., 2022). Other studies investigated an intersection safety application alert system in field trials using an on-site camera capturing traffic and identifying conflicts based on time to collision (TTC) and post encroachment time (PET) measurements (Soro et al., 2024). When both TTC and PET values were less than 3 seconds, a warning was sent out to the cyclist approaching the intersection. The results of this study showed that participants were willing to use the safety application and preferred to receive simple and clear warnings (Soro et al., 2024). Similarly, Schories et al. (2024) examined the performance of a warning triggers system for cyclists based on a TTC warning with 4 seconds. They applied this method in a virtual simulation, and the results showed positive safety benefits of avoiding a collision with a vehicle. Lastly, Hagelen et al. (2019) and Huges and Degen (2021) used radar and lidar sensors on the bicycles to scan the surroundings and estimate TTC and, in case of an imminent collision, send warnings to the cyclists. The findings of these studies indicate the potential benefits of such systems and sensors on cyclists' safety.

To increase cycling safety, researchers also designed and investigated the effectiveness of external nudging approaches aiming to adjust cyclists' behaviour (Fyhri et al., 2021; He et al., 2019; Kovaceva et al., 2022; Wallgren et al., 2020). While a viable option, this type of feedback is more rigid than having an easily adjustable on-bicycle system. However, previous research on-vehicle safety communication has mostly focused on drivers (Biondi et al., 2017; Grushko et al., 2021; Spence and Ho, 2008). Drawing from the literature on drivers, Biondi et al. (2017) found that multimodal audio-tactile warnings decreased the braking reaction time more than single modal warnings in the simulation environment. However, Geitner et al. (2019) found that audio-tactile multimodal warnings were perceived as being more startling. Strohaecker et al. (2022) studied the effectiveness of different audio and tactile modalities in different conflict scenarios. They found that audio warning was more effective since participants had shorter reaction time

compared to the tactile. Thus, in situations where the users need an urgent reaction, it is preferable. Tactile communication was found to serve better in less urgent situations (Strohaecker et al., 2022).

Erdei et al. (2020) found that cyclists most consistently responded to audio signals across different real-world environments compared to visual and tactile signals. Tactile signals performed significantly worse on rough roads. However, Erdei et al. (2020) did not consider how users perceived the different signals, which will be explored in this research. Recently, the municipality of Amsterdam conducted a field experiment in order to test users' reactions when they received warnings (Tollenaar and Plazier, 2023). They used multimodal audio-visual communication, with the visuals serving to inform the cyclist of speed warnings, and the audio serving to make participants aware of the system. However, participants mentioned low satisfaction with the manner of communication (Tollenaar and Plazier, 2023).

For the effectiveness of any warning system, perceived safety and trust are major factors (Jahanshahi et al., 2020; Nordhoff et al., 2020; Simsekoglu and Klöckner, 2019); therefore, it is important to test users' perceptions and preferences towards new technologies. Moreover, Kapousizis et al. (2024) found that perceived safety has a major role in user behavioural intention to adopt a technology, especially in the Netherlands. Kapousizis et al. (2024) also indicated that testing a smart e-bike in a real environment would capture users' preferences better, although several studies used online surveys to investigate user's preferences for an on-bicycle warning system. For instance, using an online survey, De Angelis et al. (2019) examined user preferences for warning systems with audio-visual or haptic modes; however, they did not find a significant difference between them. Nonetheless, Kapousizis et al. (under review-a, under review-b) found that such warning systems have potential and users are willing to pay for them. This means that bicycle users are open to use warning systems to improve their safety. Although there is evidence in the literature for the perceived safety and preferences of cyclists towards warning systems, the majority of existing studies used hypothetical scenarios and surveys. Soro et al. (2024) recently utilised field trials to examine perceived safety in intersections and imminent collision scenarios.

1.2. Research objective

The studies above provide valuable insights into different types of warning systems and the importance of user acceptance, however, more research is needed to examine users' opinions and acceptance of a specific context-aware cyclist warning system. This study aims to develop and test a context-aware prototype warning system to support e-bike users in high crash risk locations. For this purpose, we designed a field experiment, developed a warning system, identified high crash risk locations, designed a survey, and devised a data collection plan. The objectives of this study are as follows:

1. To investigate cyclists' perceived safety, trust and overall perception of the context-aware cyclist warning system.
2. To investigate the effect of users' riding behaviour receiving warnings from the warning system.
3. To evaluate cyclists' preferences for different communication methods and test whether the audio or haptic may offer a more intuitive interaction with the users.

The developed warning system falls to the bicycle smartness level 2, "warning assistance", based on the classification proposed by Kapousizis et al. (2024) and Kapousizis et al. (2022), which also has the highest technology readiness level. In addition, Kapousizis et al. (2024) mentioned the importance of users trying out different systems since it might influence their opinions and attitudes. Therefore, alternative communication methods were tried to identify the approaches which cyclists find valuable and motivating while not being too distracting or startling.

The rest of the paper is organised as follows: [Section 2](#) describes the methodology, field trials, system development, and data collection approach; [Section 3](#) presents the collected data and analyses of the results; [Section 4](#) discusses the results, and [Section 5](#) presents the conclusion of this paper.

2. Methodology

2.1. Fieldwork set-up

The methodology followed in this paper is divided into six parts: 1) the experiment design of the field trials, 2) the safety system design, 3) the cycling crash density model, 4) the apparatus, 5) participants recruitment, and 6) the questionnaire and collected data. [Fig. 1](#) illustrates these parts and serves as the conceptual model of this study. In detail, we designed a field experiment and used bicycle crash data to model cycling crash density. We used bicycle crash data and the road network to model cycling crash density to identify high crash risk locations using the Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) (please refer to [Section 2.2](#)). Then, we used the results of the crash density model to feed into a smartphone application to design a system to warn users via visual, audio, and tactile (vibration) notifications, which consists the context-aware warning system. In addition, we developed a survey distributed throughout the field trials to evaluate the context-aware safety support system and users' perceived safety, trust, perception, and riding behaviour changes. The results from this study could be used to further improve the system, as indicated in [Fig. 1](#). Overall, we organised field trials in Enschede, the Netherlands, including various types of infrastructure (mixed traffic, dedicated bicycle paths/lanes) to investigate how users react to receiving notifications and examine their perceived safety.

2.1.1. Field trial experiment design

A smartphone-based application was developed and was fed with high crash risk locations as identified based on the crash density model described in the following section. The aim was for participants to ride an instrumented e-bike on a predefined route and receive warnings when they approached a high-risk location to pay more attention and reduce their speed. We selected a route around the University of Twente for the field trial. The reason for this was twofold: 1) practical, we were able to host participants in the university's room, and also the bicycles were there, and 2) we were able to identify a route which was 3.4 km long with different types of infrastructure (mixed traffic, dedicated bicycle paths and bicycle lanes), with a shopping area, school zone; in a total of five high crash risk areas (four locations, one was ridden two times). [Fig. 2](#) shows the route used for the field trials.

Participants were requested to ride the same route three times.

During the first round, which served as a baseline ride, the set-up operated normally, but no information regarding road safety was given. This means the warning system was effectively turned off; only the speedometer was shown on the smartphone, as in the 'Approaching' situation in [Fig. 3](#). The function of this round was to 1) get participants familiar with the new e-bike and 2) to understand the perception and perceived safety of participants when riding this specific route with a "conventional e-bike". During the second and third ride, the warning system was turned on. Participants received warnings through either the audio or tactile modalities combined with visual information each time. In the third round, participants received warnings through the modality they had not experienced in round 2. In the high crash risk locations, participants were given an advisory speed of 20 km/h; this choice was based on pilot studies during which 18 km/h was found to be much too slow, matching the findings of [Tollenaar and Plazier \(2023\)](#), where participants indicated that advisory speeds of 10 or 15 km/h were generally too low. Navigation instructions were given to the participants through the Komoot (<https://www.komoot.com/>) on one of the smartphones.

In detail, participants rode the e-bike prototype in a predefined route. During the first ride, participants rode the prototype without receiving warnings, that is namely, as a "conventional e-bike". However, additional sensors such as GPS were used to collect speed data without influencing their riding behaviour. After the first ride, participants filled out the first part of the survey, where they stated their perceived safety, perceived trust and experience. We repeated the survey about users' perceived safety, trust, and experience when they received notifications to reduce their speed. Participants rode the prototype for the second and third ride, receiving warnings from the context-aware prototype warning system based on different modalities. Through this, we investigated how users felt when receiving notifications from the warning system, whether they were annoyed or comfortable, and their perceived safety for the context-aware warning system. Overall, we examined to what extent users were blissful as well as their riding behaviour.

Furthermore, data was collected using GPS from the smartphone, and other sensors were incorporated into the e-bikes, adding valuable characteristics in understanding participants' riding behaviour. The GPS, which was collected during the rides, allowed us to examine to what extent users followed the notifications and advice the context-aware prototype warning system provided.

2.1.2. Crash density

Bicycle crashes have been studied widely in the literature, and there are different approaches to doing so. We aim to identify high crash risk locations in Enschede and develop a safety support system using bicycle crash data. Many studies have used Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) to identify traffic crash clusters ([Abdulhafedh, 2017](#); [Anderson, 2009](#); [Ulak](#)

Fig. 1. Conceptual model of the study.

Fig. 2. Crash density map of Enschede and location of field trial route.

Fig. 3. Interaction flow of the context-aware warning system prototype.

et al., 2017). KDE is a non-parametric approach to estimating the intensity of a spatial process, which focuses on clustering pattern distributions throughout an area study region and creates a density surface of spatial point events over a 2-dimensional geographic space (Xie and Yan, 2008). However, in traffic crashes, the events occur in a network; thus, the KDE may not be a good fit (Xie and Yan, 2008). To this end, we used the Network Kernel Density Estimation (NKDE) since road crashes occur along a network, and the density needs to be estimated in a 1-D linear space rather than the Euclidean distance commonly used by the KDE. The NKDE is an extension of the classical KDE.

We used the package *spNetwork* developed by Gelb (2021) in R Core Team (2023) to proceed with the estimation, which is free and open-source software. We used the road network from the OSM (OpenStreetMap, 2023) and police crash report (BRON) data from 2016 to 2019. Fig. 2 illustrates the bicycle crash patterns in the municipality of Enschede resulting from the NKDE; lines with red represent road segments with high crash density. In addition, we used OSM data in order to identify school zones and high street locations, which were found to have a significant impact on bicycle crashes (Kapousizis et al., 2021).

2.1.3. Safety system design

The context-aware warning system proposed in this paper communicates the potentially dangerous locations to cyclists. The prototype of the warning system is created as a smartphone app using Android Studio. The context-aware warning system consists of two levels of communication: notifying and informing, similar to the set-up by Tollenaar and Plazier (2023).

The context-aware warning system comes into action when a ‘transition event’ occurs, and an overview of the event loop can be found in Fig. 3. Four such events are identified: 1) *entering*: the cyclist enters a dangerous zone; 2) *exiting*: the cyclist exits a dangerous zone; 3) *speeding up*: the cyclist speeds up from below the advisory velocity to above; and 4) *slowing down*: the cyclist retains a ‘safe’ velocity. Additionally, the *entering* event is split up into two cases: the cyclist is going above or below the advisory velocity.

Notifications are either given as audio signals through bone-conducting headphones or tactile signals through haptic gloves. Bone-conducting headphones have been chosen since they do not block any environmental sounds. Haptic gloves were chosen due to their ease of implementation, as opposed to haptic handlebars (Baldanzini et al., 2011). To minimise distraction, notifications are only sent when potential danger to the cyclist increases during the *entering* and *speeding up* transition events.

Additionally, the system aims to supply less intrusive information that provides additional understanding for the notifications. The aim is to present this information in a way that is easily accessible and understandable without providing too much distraction. The information is given through a smartphone screen as shown in Fig. 3, similar to the implementation of Tollenaar and Plazier (2023). The smartphone screen is set to red when the cyclist is going above the advisory speed and is set to green when the cyclist is going below the advisory speed. Only the speedometer is shown on normal segments without increased safety issues.

2.1.4. Apparatus

Participants were riding a smart e-bike prototype on a predefined route starting at the University of Twente, the Netherlands. The field trial - set up/data collection/recruitment- was a joint work of PhD students as part of the Smart Connected Bikes project (<https://www.smartconnectedbikes.nl/>). Therefore, the prototype bike incorporated multiple sensors to collect data for different research projects. Not all collected sensor data is used in this paper.

For this research, the e-bike was equipped with two Nokia C32 TA-1524 smartphones. One of the smartphones served as a prototype of the context-aware warning system and for GPS measurements; the other

was used for navigation. Participants were asked to wear bHaptics TactGlove DK2 haptic gloves or Shokz OpenMove S661 bone conduction headphones for the warning system during the second or third round.

Additionally, for related research, one forward-facing GoPro 3 action camera and three Inertia ProMove Miniwere IMU sensors were mounted on the bicycle. Two of the three IMU sensors were attached to the bicycle frame to measure road surface quality, one to the pedal. In addition, participants were asked to wear a helmet to which another Inertia ProMove Miniwere IMU sensor was attached. Participants also wore an Empatica E4 wristband and a Polar H10 heart rate sensor. Finally, participants were also asked to use a button press system to indicate their experience during the rides.

The audio signal consists of two 780hz signals of 300 ms with a 20 ms pause. This is the same frequency is as used by Erdei et al. (2020). They used two signals of 650 ms instead of 300 ms. However, the shorter duration is chosen since it can be argued that an (unnecessarily) long signal can be more distracting. The phone volume was set to 50 %. Following Erdei et al. (2020), the tactile signal consists of two pulses of 250 ms with a 400 ms pause, however, it is not possible to extract the frequency from the bHaptics interface.

The bicycle was equipped with different hardware features, such as two smartphones, one to give directions to users and the other to communicate safety warning messages, as indicated in Fig. 4.

2.1.5. Participants recruitment

The field trial, along with a questionnaire, was conducted between April and May 2024 in Enschede, the Netherlands. The questionnaire was developed using Maptionnaire (Burnett et al., 2023) and was filled out by the participants during the field trials.

The target population were people 1) older than 18 years, 2) who have been cycling on average at least once per month in the past six months, 3) without the influence of illicit drugs, and 4) without medication that is issued with advice against, or prohibition against, participating in traffic. We used different channels to recruit participants, such as mailing lists of the University of Twente and Saxion University of Applied Sciences, advertisements in online press (U-Today), local cycling unions in the city of Enschede, portal news of the municipality of Enschede, the Enschede Fiets app and personal social media. The field trials with the questionnaire had a completion time of around 1.5 hours. Each participant received a voucher worth €10 as a token of appreciation for their time. In total, 46 participants were recruited and participated in the field trials.

Before the field trials started, initial pilots with the instrumented e-bikes took place to test that all sensors worked properly and that the set-up was feasible. In addition, we tested the survey; we first piloted it

Fig. 4. Bicycle set-up.

within the research group and later with some participants. Once the pilot of the field trials and the survey were successful, the survey was translated into Dutch by native speakers within the research group and tested once more to ensure the readability and consistency of the translation.

2.1.6. Questionnaire

Enschede has a population of around 150 thousand inhabitants, with a dense cycling infrastructure as do most Dutch cities. The city of Enschede has international influences since the University of Twente is located there, and there are many international and high-tech companies. Thus, the survey was translated into Dutch and English to account for both native and foreign citizens. Note that the survey was developed in English, and two pilots were used to ensure the optimal structure and reliability of the questions. Thus, the questionnaire was distributed among researchers from our groups, and after two iterations, we translated the survey into Dutch. In total, 46 participants joined the field trials. After cleaning the data, 41 were analysed; two participants did not complete the rides due to rain, and three participants experienced technical issues, so we decided to exclude them. All participants completed three rounds: 25 completed the second round using audio warnings and the third round with the tactile, while 16 completed the second round with the tactile communication and the third round with audio warnings. The number of experiments that resulted from audio and tactile warnings was merely due to the availability of the equipment.

Questions in the survey for this research were divided into two parts: 1) questions related to sociodemographic statistics, participants' general mobility habits, and participants' perceived safety and experiences when they cycle in their daily lives; 2) questions about the participants' opinions on the context-aware warning system. Note that the second part was repeated three times, once after each ride. Participants received a written information brief about the steps of the field trials as well as an oral explanation. Initially, participants were requested to fill out the first part of the survey, which consisted of sociodemographic information as mentioned above. Then, participants were requested to proceed by riding the bicycle. During this ride, no warnings were given through the prototype. Once the ride was completed, participants filled out the second part of the survey. Then, participants received an explanation of the safety support system and a set of 5-Likert scale questions about their expectations of the system. The explanation of the context-aware warning system given to the participants during the survey was as follows:

"In our research, we want to evaluate the design and effects of a warning system. The system warns you to avoid collisions with other road users. The warnings are given at hazardous locations, through visual, audio and/or vibration signals. We would like to ask you some questions about your expectations of this system."

Then, participants continued with the second and third rides, during which warnings were given when entering critical locations. [Table 1](#) presents an overview of the questions we used in the survey.

2.2. Research methods

In this study, we had two main sources of collected data: 1) survey data and 2) GPS data, which was collected using smartphones. Participants' answers to the survey give us information about their perception of the context-aware warning system. At the same time, GPS data allows us to assess the effects of the system based on different modalities on participants' riding behaviour, specifically in speed reduction.

We calculated the average speed of the participants 5-seconds before and after the point they were supposed to receive a warning. The GPS used during the field trials had 1 Hz accuracy, recording 1 point per second. After testing the context-aware support system, we used a 5-second window as the proper time to allow participants to react after

Table 1
Overview of the questions used.

Category	Question	Source
Perceived safety	I would feel safe with the Warning System.	(Jahanshahi et al., 2020; Kapousizis et al., 2024) and own investigation
	I think with the Warning System I can increase my safety	
	I think that riding with the Warning System can reduce the risk of me getting involved in a crash compared to a conventional bike	
Perceived trust	I think that there will be fewer crashes for users with the Warning System.	(Hinderks et al., 2018; Kapousizis et al., 2024; Nordhoff et al., 2020; Venkatesh et al., 2012)
	I would trust the Warning System	
	I will ride with more stress using the Warning System.	
	I would like to use the Warning System.	
	I think the Warning System would be easy to use.	
Perceived performance	I expect that the capabilities of the Warning System will meet my requirements.	(Hinderks et al., 2018) and own investigation
	Useful to useless	
	Assisting to worthless	
	Undesirable to desirable	
	Understandable to badly understandable	
	Raising alertness to reducing alertness	
	Noticeable to badly noticeable	
Motivating to Very demotivating		

receiving a warning. Thus, we used 5-second windows before and after high crash risk locations.

Initially, we used t-tests to examine whether speed reductions in high crash risk locations differed by personal characteristics, such as gender, and usage of e-bike and conventional bicycle and if they were statistically significant. We used 299 speed points for the three rides for the "SlowDown" event to examine whether participants reduced their speed when initially receiving the warnings.

We further examined users' speed reduction after receiving system warnings by applying a Multinomial Logit model (MNL) to the collected data. We refer readers to the following study for more information about the MNL (McFadden, 1973). We estimated two MNLs to analyse participants' speed when they approached a high crash risk location and their speed when they received warnings to reduce their speed. For this part of the analysis, we used the "entering", "slow down", and "slow-down reminder" since these are the cases in which participants receive notifications. In total, we used 1560 warnings, 524 warning points for audio communication, and 592 for tactile communication. The remaining 444 data points are from the first ride (baseline) participants completed and were supposed to receive warnings. In order to perform the analysis, we used the five-second average speed before and after the warnings.

3. Results

3.1. Data statistics

As mentioned earlier, 41 participants were included in the analysis after the data cleaning. The mean age of participants was 42.1 (SD = 15.65) and ranged from 25 to 75 years of age; 73 % were males (n = 30), and 63 % (n = 26) earned a university degree. In addition, 73 % (n = 30) of the participants use a bicycle weekly, more than four days a week, while only 22 % (n = 9) use an e-bike weekly, meaning they have a quite good cycling experience. None of the participants used a Speed-Pedelec in a related question we asked. The sample distribution can be

found in Table 2.

3.2. Perceived safety and trust

Participants' scores for perceived safety and trust based on a 5-Likert scale of questions are shown in Figs. 5 and 6. Participants completed a repeated survey after every ride (without intervention, with audio and visual, and tactile and visual). Thus, we were able to capture participants' opinions about the context-aware warning system.

As shown in Fig. 5, question Q1: *I would feel safe with the Warning System* indicated that participants felt safer with the warning system compared to the baseline, especially with tactile communication. The second question, Q2: *I think the Warning System I can increase my safety*, shows that participants had higher expectations since the score for the baseline has the highest value, while the audio and tactile come slightly after. In addition, we notice that while there was 22 % "Neutral" in the baseline, later, after the rides, participants shifted to the negative side and felt less safe with the tactile warning.

Regarding Q3: *I think that riding with the Warning System can reduce the risk of me getting involved in a crash compared to a conventional bike*; we see that for the baseline, 44 % of participants believed that the Warning System would decrease their risk of involvement in a crash, and 34 % was neutral. However, after the rides, the neutral percentage shifted to the negative side since the percentages were 27 % for the audio and 34 % for the tactile. This means that participants were not fully convinced that the warning system could increase their safety compared to a conventional bicycle.

For the last question, Q4: *I think that there will be fewer crashes for users with the Warning System*; 49 % of the participants had a neutral opinion, 44 % positive and only 7 % negative for the baseline. However, we see that after using the warning system, participants have a positive opinion

Table 2
Sample composition.

Variable	Sample	
	Count	Percentage
Number of respondents	41	100 %
Gender		
Male	30	73 %
Female	11	27 %
Age		
<25	4	10 %
25–35	18	44 %
36–45	2	5 %
46–55	7	17 %
56–65	5	12 %
66–75	4	10 %
>75	1	2 %
Education		
Low (high school or lower)	6	15 %
Vocational (Technical)	8	20 %
High (university degree or higher)	26	63 %
Other	1	2 %
Net monthly individual income (€/month)		
up to 3000	26	63 %
More than 3000	15	37 %
E-bike usage		
Never or less than 1 day per year	25	61 %
1–5 days per year	6	15 %
6–11 days per year	1	2 %
1–3 days per month	-	0 %
1–3 days per week	2	5 %
4 days or more per week	7	17 %
Conventional bicycle usage		
Never or less than 1 day per year	6	15 %
1–5 days per year	-	0 %
6–11 days per year	2	5 %
1–3 days per month	3	7 %
1–3 days per week	4	10 %
4 days or more per week	26	63 %

in this regard, especially for the tactile warning. Overall, we see that during the first round of questions (before the participants experience the system) it seems that they keep a neutral attitude, while this changes after the rides. In addition, we see a shift from neutral to negative, implying that participants were less satisfied. However, we also found that participants had a positive opinion about the context-aware warning system for three out of the four questions.

Regarding participants' trust for the context-aware warning system, as shown by Fig. 6, participants' scores for Q1: *I would trust/trusted the Warning System*, are in the middle, with 37 % indicating a positive opinion for the baseline. After participants rode the e-bike with the warning system, their trust reduced to 23 % for the audio warnings; for the tactile, their trust remained at 37 %. However, most participants had a negative opinion in both audio and tactile settings, indicating a low trust in the system. Regarding Q2: *I will ride/rode with more stress using the Warning System*; for the baseline, the majority of the participants expected to feel lower stress. However, they mentioned that they felt higher stress using the Warning System, especially for the tactile.

About question 3, Q3: *I would (like to) use the Warning System*, most of the participants have a negative opinion, with only 21 % and 28 % having a positive opinion of the audio and tactile, correspondingly. Q4: *I think the Warning System would be/was easy to use*, we see that the majority of the participants have a positive opinion, with 79 % thinking that tactile is easy to use and 67 % for the audio. It is important to mention that before the rides, 44 % of the participants had a neutral opinion, which changed after the rides. Regarding the last question, Q5: *I (expect) that the capabilities of the Warning System will meet/met my requirements*, the positive answers have remained similar between the baseline and the rides; however, half of the participants initially had a neutral opinion (before they try out the e-bike), they shifted to negative ones.

3.3. Perceived performance

During the survey and field trials, participants were also asked to evaluate the warnings they received on a number of scales. The resulting scores the participants gave can be found in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8. Participants were asked for this evaluation after rides 2 and 3.

As can be found in Fig. 7, most participants indicated that they found both the audio and tactile warnings noticeable. As many as 97 % of the participants found the tactile warnings noticeable, while 73 % found the audio warning noticeable. The scores for alertness are mostly towards raising alertness, although some participants did feel like the system reduced their alertness (51 % for audio and 53 % for tactile). Regarding the scores for motivating the system, most participants had a neutral attitude, while only 32 % had a positive opinion for the audio and 36 % for the tactile. Lastly, participants evaluated to what extent the warnings were understandable, with most participants (78 %) indicating that they found the tactile clear, while the audio was only 49 %.

Participants' opinions on the context-aware warning system's usefulness and desirability varied (Fig. 8). In detail, 36 % of the participants found the tactile warning useful, and 41 % found the audio useful. Regarding the system's desirability, 29 % of the participants gave a positive score for the audio and tactile aspects. However, we noticed that a high proportion of the participants had a neutral opinion for both questions.

3.4. Riding behaviour changes

First, we compared participants' speed for the baseline ride (without intervention) against the rides with the intervention. We applied the same for the rides with the interventions. We calculated the average speed for all the locations, before and after warnings, and found that participants reduced their speed by 1.3 kilometres per hour after intervention.

In addition, we ran t-tests in order to examine the difference in

Fig. 5. 5-point Likert scale questions related to perceived safety.

average speed between the two groups. In detail, we used the ride without intervention as a baseline and compared it with the audio and tactile interventions (Table 3). The average speed for all three rides was almost the same before a warning was communicated to the users (baseline: 22.9 km/h, audio: 23.1 km/h and tactile: 23.0 km/h). After the warning, users reduced their speed on average by 1.2 km/h and 1.4 km/h for audio and tactile, correspondingly.

Fig. 9 shows the average speeds before and after the warnings for the individual modalities, audio and tactile, in the average 5-second windows before and after participants enter a high crash risk location, and the average speeds for both modalities.

Furthermore, as mentioned earlier (Section 2.1), in our experiment, we used a route with five different high crash risk locations (one was a school location), where participants were receiving warnings. Thus, we also compared participants' speeds before and after warnings in the different locations. We compared the participants' speeds when entering a location without and with the context-aware warning system, and we found that participants had lower speeds after receiving warnings when they entered high crash risk locations, and the speed reduction was almost equal in all locations.

3.5. Factors affecting speed reduction

Table 4 presents the test results based on different types of warnings and the different variables that were used. Males were found to have a higher speed reduction than females in both types of warnings. For the audio, males had a reduction of 1.2 km/h (p-value < 0.001) and females only 0.6 km/h; similar rates were found for the tactile 1.3 km/h (p-value < 0.001) for males and 0.9 km/h for females after they received the warnings. The differences in speed reduction were not significant for female participants. Females were found to cycle with an average speed of 21.8 km/h before receiving a warning, while males 23.5 km/h; females used to cycle 1.7 km/h slower than males. Therefore, both males and females reduced their speed; however, speed reduction for the males was higher since they generally approached a critical location with a higher speed.

The last variables we tested were the usage of bicycles weekly or not and types, such as e-bikes and conventional bicycles. We tested participants using an e-bike on a weekly base (more than one time per week) against those who do not use an e-bike weekly. We found that both groups reduced their speed by 1.1 km/h after receiving audio and 1.4 km/h when receiving tactile warnings. However, only the non-

Fig. 6. 5-point Likert scale questions related to trust.

weekly e-bike users were found to have a significant difference. This is probably due to the small number of weekly e-bike users. For the conventional bicycle users using a bicycle weekly, it was found that a speed reduction of 0.9 km/h for audio and 1.3 km/h for tactile warnings were both significant, with a p-value < 0.05. However, for the other group, participants using a bicycle less than once a week, were found to have non-significant differences again due to the small number of participants in this group. We also considered controlling for multiple corrections by using, for instance, the Bonferroni correction; however, since this study was exploratory and restricted to a few, not simultaneous, comparisons, we did not use any corrections (Armstrong, 2014; Lee and Lee, 2018;

Streiner and Norman, 2011).

Furthermore, we estimated a MNL and used the following categories:

- 0: participants did not follow the recommendation;
- 1: participants reduced their speed up to 1 km/h;
- 2: participants reduced their speed between 1 and 2 km/h;
- 3: participants reduced their speed by more than 2 km/h.

We estimated two models, one for the audio warnings and one for the tactile. Table 5 and Table 6 present the results correspondingly. During the model estimation, we used the category “0: no speed reduction” as a

Fig. 7. 5-point Likert scale evaluation of the warning system for different scales related to the perceived performance.

Fig. 8. 5-point Likert scale evaluation of the context-aware warning system for different scales related to the perceived usefulness and desirability of the system.

Table 3

T-test for speed difference (baseline, audio and tactile).

Type	Mean before	Mean after	Mean diff	SD before	SD after	p-value	t value	df
Baseline	22.94	22.50	0.44	2.62	2.12	0.222	1.22	166.73
Audio	23.17	21.95	1.22	1.97	2.52	0.001	3.91	196.62
Tactile	23.03	21.61	1.42	1.98	2.33	0.001	4.78	204.81

reference category and the comparison made against it.

Audio: The results of the rest of the categories are as follows: gender (males) has negative betas in the first two reduction categories (0–1 and 1–2 km/h reduction) ($\beta = -0.276$ $\beta = -0.198$), while for the third category (more than 2 km/h reduction) it was found that to be a positive beta ($\beta = 0.687$), meaning that males are less likely to reduce their speed by 0–2 km/h than the females. Also, males are more likely to reduce their speed by two kilometres than females. Age was used as a dummy variable here and the comparison between participants older than 55

against the rest of the age groups. A positive beta was found only for the last category (reduction of more than 2 km/h), but still no significant difference with the base category (participants younger than 55). Participants using an e-bike weekly are more likely to reduce their speed by 0–1 km/h or 1–2 km/h, compared to participants not using an e-bike weekly. With the category 1–2 km/h reduction to be significant (p-value = 0.042). Regarding the last variable, participants who use a conventional bicycle weekly, it was found that they are less likely to reduce their speed by more than 2 km/h compared to participants using a

Fig. 9. Average speed before and after warnings based on different modalities.

Table 4
t-Test for different sociodemographic groups and warning types.

	Type	Mean before	Mean after	Mean diff	SD before	SD after	p-value	t value	df
Audio	Males	23.67	22.43	1.25	1.87	2.61	0.001	3.385	136.070
	Females	22.00	21.44	0.56	1.65	1.73	0.423	0.817	21.947
	e-bike weekly	23.29	22.18	1.11	1.88	2.35	0.261	1.162	17.165
	No e-bike weekly	23.46	22.31	1.15	1.94	2.55	0.002	3.191	143.570
	Bicycle weekly	23.49	22.61	0.88	1.86	2.19	0.010	2.592	136.35
	No bicycle weekly	23.24	20.97	2.27	2.19	3.33	0.027	2.338	27.705
Tactile	Males	23.37	21.99	1.38	2.10	2.52	0.001	3.760	153.140
	Females	21.68	20.77	0.91	1.74	1.54	0.207	1.304	19.708
	e-bike weekly	22.33	20.77	1.56	1.98	1.95	0.114	1.674	15.997
	No e-bike weekly	23.26	21.96	1.30	2.13	2.48	0.001	3.594	158.520
	Bicycle weekly	23.23	21.93	1.30	2.11	2.41	0.001	3.550	149.330
	No bicycle weekly	22.83	21.37	1.46	2.27	2.66	0.133	1.554	25.347

Table 5
Model results for audio warnings.

Variables	0–1 km/h reduction		1–2 km/h reduction		More than 2 km/h reduction	
	Beta	St. Error	Beta	St. Error	Beta	St. Error
(Intercept)	-0.960	0.595	-3.827	1.219	-1.333*	0.750
gender (male)	-0.276	0.403	-0.198	0.613	0.687	0.654
Age group ≥ 56	-0.265	0.446	-0.899	0.806	0.688	0.497
E-bike (weekly)	0.055	0.684	2.163**	1.063	-1.102	0.825
Bicycle (weekly)	-0.194	0.509	1.769	1.170	-1.438***	0.493

*** : p-value < 0.001,
** : p-value < 0.05,
* : p-value < 0.1.

Table 6
Model results for tactile warnings.

Variables	0–1 km/h reduction		1–2 km/h reduction		More than 2 km/h reduction	
	Beta	St. Error	Beta	St. Error	Beta	St. Error
(Intercept)	-0.543	0.493	-2.463***	0.7223	-2.405**	0.783
gender (male)	-0.568	0.359	-0.107	0.503	0.660	0.647
Age group ≥ 56	-0.517	0.396	-0.004	0.471	0.604	0.446
E-bike (weekly)	0.631	0.503	1.247**	0.607	-0.235	0.705
Bicycle (weekly)	0.147	0.417	0.930	0.637	0.032	0.554

*** : p-value < 0.001, ** : p-value < 0.05, * : p-value < 0.1.

bicycle less often; ($\beta = -1.438$, p-value = 0.003).

Tactile: Regarding the model results for the tactile warnings, we found that, again, males are more likely to reduce their speed by more

than 2 km/h compared to females. Additionally, we found that participants of the age group older than 56 have negative estimates, for the first two categories (0–1 km/h and 1–2 km/h reduction), meaning that they are less likely to reduce their speed compared to females. However, they are more likely to reduce their speed by more than 2 km/h compared to females. Participants who use an e-bike weekly are more likely to reduce their speed up to 2 km/h ($\beta = 1.247$, p -value = 0.04) compared to participants using an e-bike less. Finally, participants using a conventional bicycle weekly are more likely to reduce their speed in all categories than those using a conventional bicycle a few times a month or less.

Furthermore, the first model for audio indicates that frequent bicycle users have negative estimates in the last speed category (more than 2 km/h reduction) and at a significant confidence level, while we do not find similar results for the tactile warning. Overall, we did not find statistically significant differences for most of the variables in both warnings, audio and tactile, probably due to the small number of participants and data points. These results, therefore, need to be interpreted with caution.

4. Discussion of the results

4.1. Explaining users' perceived safety and trust

Participants in this study evaluated the safety support system. In detail, we see that participants have a higher perceived safety for the system in questions Q1: *I would feel safe with the Warning System*, Q2: *I think the Warning System I can increase my safety*, and Q4: *I think that there will be fewer crashes for users with the Warning System* compared to the baseline before they ride the instrumented e-bike. Only in question, Q2: *I think the Warning System I can increase my safety* participants scored higher for the baseline than the audio and tactile scenarios. What stands out in this analysis is that more than half of the participants have a positive opinion of the safety support system. In addition, we notice a higher preference towards tactile communication since it gives them a higher perceived safety compared to the audio; however, this difference is small. Thus, we can see that the system increased participants' perceived safety. Perceived safety was found to be a significant factor in user acceptance of the behavioural intention of a smart e-bike (Kapousizis et al., 2024).

Interestingly, the effect of trust in the system is lower compared to the perceived safety. We found that participants had higher expectations based on what they got, which is reflected in their scores regarding their trust in the safety support system. Less than half of the participants trust the system, and only in question Q4: *I think that there will be fewer crashes for users with the Warning System* did around 70 % state that the system is easy to use. In other words, we found that participants in this study considered the system easy to use, which was also found to be a significant factor in accepting smart bicycle technologies by Kapousizis et al. (2024). While participants show a high perceived safety for the system, potential users of this system need to be convinced and trust the system as well. Thus, we believe that a system with fewer devices in the handlebar will be more trustworthy than the current one (Fig. 3). Overall, improvements in the system's set-up are suggested to improve the system's trust since it also affects user acceptance in other studies (Kapsner and Abdelrahman, 2020; Kim et al., 2024).

4.2. Explaining users' riding behaviour changes

The average speed of the participants during the first round was found to be higher compared to the rounds with the speed interventions. In detail, we estimated the average speed before and after a participant received a warning. For the baseline round, we found that participants did not change their speed when approaching a high crash risk location; however, they did reduce their speed by almost 2 km/h during the second and third rounds when they received warnings. This means that

the intervention was effective, which may result in reducing crash risk due to the high speed, which was found to be a significant factor associated with e-bike crashes (Kapousizis et al., 2024; Stelling et al., 2021). Similar studies using a bicycle simulator also found that warnings influenced participants to reduce speed and increased users' perceived safety regardless of age group (Kreißig et al., 2022; Linder et al., 2024).

Furthermore, regarding the effectiveness of the two different nudging systems, we found that the average speed with the tactile warnings was slightly lower than the audio (0.2 km/h difference). While this speed difference is small, this result is in line with Strohaecker et al. (2022) since they found that audio warnings had a shorter reaction time compared to tactile, which might influence the speed reduction of the users as well. Nonetheless, in our study, some participants mentioned that they did not always hear the audio communication since the bone-conducting headphones were sometimes shifted due to the helmet, which might influence the speed difference between the two modalities.

4.3. Explaining speed reduction

We explained the speed reduction by comparing participants with different sociodemographic characteristics and mobility habits using t -test group differences and MNL model. The information on sociodemographic characteristics and mobility habits was collected from the survey, as explained in Section 2.6.

As indicated in Section 3.5, and based on the t -test we estimated, we found that both males and females reduced their speed when approaching a high crash risk location, meaning they followed the warnings from both audio and tactile communication channels. However, we found that speed reduction for males was higher than for females since males were found to ride at a higher speed compared to females in our field experiment. These results are in line with the results from the MNL model since we found that males are more likely to reduce their speed by 2 km/h, in both communication channels as well. Even though males had a higher speed reduction after receiving a warning, their speed was still higher than the females' speed (22.4 km/h vs 21.4 km/h for audio warnings and 22.0 km/h vs 20.8 km/h for tactile).

Regarding the different age groups that were tested, we found that participants aged 25–35 had a significant speed reduction. The same applies to participants who fall in the age group above 55 since they reduced their speed in both types of warning (1.6 km/h and 1.7 km/h, for audio and tactile, correspondingly). Participants older 55 were found to be more likely to reduce their speed by 2 km/h during the MNL model. Participants between 36–55 years old, while reduced their cycling speed in both warning types, were not found to have a significant difference in the statistical tests. This is likely due to the low number of participants in this age group. A comparison of the findings with those of other studies confirms that middle-aged and older individuals are less likely to follow the warning and use warning systems (Soro et al., 2024).

We also found that participants who use e-bikes weekly showed no significant difference again, probably due to this group's low number of members. Positive speed reduction was also found in the MNL model, with only a statistically significant difference for the group 1–2 km/h reduction. Participants using a conventional bicycle weekly were found to have a significant difference before and after the warnings in both communication types (audio and tactile) since, on average, they reduced their speed by almost 2 km/h. Regarding the MNL model, we found that participants who use a conventional bicycle weekly were less likely to reduce their speed by more than 2 km/h than non-conventional bicycle users. The findings align with a recent study by Soro et al. (2024), which found that participants using a bicycle weekly were more likely to use an intersection system alert than those cycling less. Lastly, participants older 55 were found to be more likely to reduce their speed by 2 km/h in the MNL model, but this result is not statistically significant.

4.4. Policy and practical implications of the study

This study proved the usefulness and effectiveness of an early safety support system for e-bike users since it positively influences the perceived safety of the users and riding behaviour. Bicycle manufacturers and system designers could consider integrating such a warning system on the e-bikes since we found that 1) a significant number of participants felt safer using this system and 2) the potential of reducing the crash risk is high due to the significant speed reduction. Due to the low scores for trust in this system, we recommend that bicycle manufacturers and designers improve the system's quality to reach a higher technology readiness level before they consider further field trials (Kapousizis et al., 2022). This can be done by implementing the system on the bicycle rather than using smartphones, which happened during the field trials. Policymakers may consider creating new policies to promote the context-aware warning system or similar to a specific group of more vulnerable e-bike users, such as elderly cyclists. Integrating such warning systems into fast e-bikes might help reduce the probability of e-bike users being involved in crashes, especially due to the high speed.

4.5. Limitations and future work

A limitation of this study is that participants used the prototype along a predefined route under a structured field trial, which may influence their riding behaviour. Thus, we recommend that future studies run long-term field trials to assess the effects of a warning system under natural conditions and how participants cycle in everyday life. In addition, the bicycle manufacturers could develop and test smart e-bike prototypes and let potential buyers try them out in their test centres. The benefits of such experiments will be twofold: on the one hand, to promote smart bicycle technologies and, on the other hand, to get better insights into potential consumers' preferences on different technologies on e-bikes.

Furthermore, in this study, we did not consider the reason for each user trip, i.e., travelling for leisure or on a commute trip home-to-work, since people may react differently based on the trip characteristics. Another point for attention is the small number of participants, which may affect the validity and generalizability of the findings. Also, the gender and age discrepancy in the sample may have affected the findings. Thus, future studies can focus on recruiting a larger and more representative sample of cyclists.

The effectiveness of the on-bicycle communication heavily depends on the implementation. The bone-conducting headphones were difficult to combine with the helmets at times. This might have caused the headphones to shift, decreasing the audibility. For ease of implementation, haptic gloves were used rather than, for example, haptic handlebars (Baldanzini et al., 2011). The aim was to evaluate the feasibility of haptic feedback rather than this exact implementation. Participants in this field trial were asked to cycle using the Komoot navigation app. Exploring other options, such as using physical signs, is recommended for future research. In this research, it turned out that participants found it difficult to navigate along the route. Another point for attention is the unbalanced number of participants over the order of conditions due to the equipment's availability.

The survey had open questions where participants could indicate their opinions about the context-aware prototype warning system. Some participants liked the audio volume, while others indicated the audio was barely audible. The current set-up worked with a fixed volume, and in the final product, it should be adjustable to the user's hearing. Additionally, the combination of headphones and the helmet may have shifted the headphones a little, making the signal less audible. Furthermore, multiple participants indicated that "the sound could not be heard when there was wind." This raises questions about the suitability of the headphones. Therefore, in the future, the system may benefit from further finetuning.

In this study, we used BRON dataset, which underrepresents cycling

crashes compared to ambulance datasets, however, the latter is not available for the whole country yet (Pijlic, 2024). In addition, crash data also do not necessarily match with perceived safety levels (Uijtewilligen, 2024), which might also affect trust in user support systems. In addition, we used a spatial analysis approach (KDE) to identify high crash risk locations. However, crash specific factors such as the time, date (of the bicycle crashes), age, and gender (of cyclists in those crashes) were not taken into account to identify user and time specific crash risks. We recommend further research to create risk profiles for different user groups, i.e., elderly users, since different ages have a different probability of being involved in a crash and provide personalised safety warnings. Also, we believe that developing a dynamic model that considers all the above information, including weather conditions, and sends real-time updates will also be of interest.

A further study is suggested to focus on different types of communication, such as helmets with integrated audio or lights that warn users when they approach a high crash risk location. Another potentially fruitful research would be to investigate users' perceived safety and trust of a speed adaptation system, which would reduce the assistance of the e-bike or decelerate when approaching high crash risk locations rather than the context-aware warning system we examined in this paper.

5. Conclusion

E-bikes have the potential to reduce car usage by replacing cars for short to medium distance trips. Nonetheless, as it is easier to ride e-bikes faster than conventional bicycles, they are riskier, especially for those unfamiliar with the high speed (Schleinitz and Petzoldt, 2023). Cycling safety has been a persistent issue in many countries, including the Netherlands, especially in the last few years with e-bikes.

In this study, we showed that integrating a safety support system into e-bikes can be instrumental in reducing crash risks. To do so, we tested the effects of the designed safety support system on users' perceived safety, trust, and riding behaviour. We verified that the designed system could influence cyclist riding behaviour and perceived safety. The key findings are summarised below as follow:

- Participants were found to have a higher perceived safety for the e-bike equipped with a safety support system than a conventional e-bike.
- Although participants found the system easy to use, positively influencing their acceptance, their general trust was low.
- The mean speed of the participants during the rides, baseline and with intervention, was found to be lower for the rides with the intervention. This proves that the system positively influences users' riding behaviour for speed reduction.
- Males were found to have a higher speed reduction after the advice from the system to reduce their speed compared to females. However, females entered a high crash location with a lower speed than males.
- Participants who use an e-bike or conventional bicycle weekly are more likely to reduce their speed with audio warnings than tactile warnings.

To conclude, the results of this study prove that the context-aware warning system positively influences users' perceived safety and perceived performance. Furthermore, we found that participants' slowed down, implying a riding behaviour change when they rode with the context-aware warning prototype system. In this study, we examined a potential smart bike technology corresponding to smartness level 2; however, there is room for further investigation of other smart bicycle technologies with higher bicycle smartness levels (Kapousizis et al., 2022). Our study showed that there is potential for adopting similar and more advanced systems waiting to be unlocked by researchers and bicycle manufacturers.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Georgios Kapousizis: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Karst Geurs:** Conceptualization. **M. Baran Ulak:** Writing – review & editing. **Annemarie Jutte:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declared that there is no conflict of Interest.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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